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*Sven-Olof Yrjö Collin***MOTIVATIONS TO HUMAN ACTION:
SELFISHNESS, BELONGINGNESS AND DUTY**

Teaching in business programs use models that assume human motivation to be mainly directed by selfishness or belongingness. But humans also have the motive of duty, to do the right thing. We need to consider duty in order to give a fuller image and explanation of humans and their motives to action. I present the concept of duty in contrast to selfishness and belongingness.

Key words: Duty, human motivation, selfishness, belongingness.

Коллин Свен-Олоф. Источники человеческой мотивации: эгоизм, чувство принадлежности и долг.

Дисциплины, читаемые в университетах в рамках образовательных программ по бизнесу, традиционно считают основными факторами, определяющими мотивацию индивидуума в бизнесе, эгоизм (инстинктивное стремление к преимуществам для себя) и чувство принадлежности к определенному сообществу. Автор данного исследования утверждает, что человеком зачастую руководит мотив долга, стремление поступать «правильно», в соответствии со своим представлением о долге. Автор считает необходимым учитывать мотив долга для более полного представления о человеческом поведении и мотивах тех или иных поступков. В статье концепция «долга» представлена в противовес инстинктам эгоизма и групповой принадлежности. Автор обращает внимание на то, что человеческий инстинкт действовать в соответствии со своим долгом менее изучен и возросший интерес к данному феномену обусловлен растущим интересом к бизнес-этике.

Автор также обращает внимание на тот факт, что в определенных обстоятельствах одни мотивы поведения могут быть востребованы более, чем другие. К примеру, в ситуациях с высокой степенью неопределенности востребованы индивидуумы, в своих поступках руководствующиеся мотивом долга.

Ключевые слова: долг, мотивация человека, эгоизм, чувство принадлежности.

Коллін Свен-Олоф. Джерела людської мотивації: егоїзм, почуття приналежності, обов'язок.

Дисципліни, що викладаються в рамках освітніх програм з бізнесу, факторами, що визначають мотивацію бізнес-активності, традиційно вважають егоїзм (прагнення отримати найкраще для себе) та відчуття приналежності до певної спільноти. Автор дослідження доводить, що разом із цими факторами людиною керує мотив обов'язку, бажання вчиняти правильно, згідно свого уявлення про обов'язок. Автор вважає за необхідне приймати до уваги мотив обов'язку для формування повного уявлення про поведінку людини та мотивацію людських вчинків. В статті концепція обов'язку розглянута в протиставленні інстинктам егоїзму та приналежності до спільноти. Автор звертає увагу на той факт, що інстинкт діяти згідно обов'язку є менш дослідженим в науковій літературі, а інтерес до цього фактору обумовлений актуальністю бізнес-етики в сучасному світі.

Також автор звертає увагу на той факт, що в різних середовищах різні мотивації можуть бути більш або менш затребувані в суспільстві. Автору належить гіпотеза про те, що в середовищах з високим рівнем невизначеності, затребувані індивідууми, дії яких мотивує обов'язок.

Ключові слова: обов'язок, мотивація людини, егоїзм, відчуття приналежності до спільноти.

Introduction

Teaching in business programs involves presenting the major theories and their basic assumptions of human behaviour. Through our teaching we not only give knowledge, but we also influence the views of the students and ultimately even influence their behaviour. It has been claimed that education in business program foster egoism and lower levels of moral reasoning (Brandon et al., 2007; Scofield et al., 2004). While it could partly be explained by selection, it can be assumed that business education influences the student's attitudes. It should therefore be of outmost importance that the education covers all aspects of human behaviour. In this paper, I will put an emphasis on our basic assumptions of human behaviour and that we have to be able to deal with three motives of human action, selfishness, belongingness and duty.

In economics and in corporate governance (CG), which is my specialised field, we use self-interest as the founding motive influencing human decision

making and action. It can be defined as an individual performing an action because the individual will achieve a personal benefit (Cropanzano, Goldman and Folger, 2005), and it resides explicitly in agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). In CG we also use a motive we can term belongingness (Gere and MacDonald, 2010) as a complementary motive. It can be defined as an individuals tendency to be attracted and to belong to a group, and to adjust to the norms of the group, for example norms of reciprocity and equity, through internalizing norms, i.e., become socialized, or to act in a way that is considered to be legitimate. This conception resides in theories such as institutional theory (DiMaggio & Powell, 1991), and theories using the Weberian conception of value rational (wertrational) action (Swedberg, 2007). Both assumptions are teleological models of humans, stressing the desired consequence of an action. They have been explained as ultimately evolutionary instincts drawing on the recent development in evolutionary psychology where they have been seen as selected due to supporting inclusive fitness and altruism (Boehm, 1997).

During the last 10 years a deontological model has appeared, assuming duty as a motive for human action. It can be defined as an individual performing an act since it is right according to the individual's system of beliefs to perform the act, and in contrast to the other two motives, it is action without considering the consequences of the action. Duty as a motive resides today mainly in organizational justice theories (Turillo, Folger, Lavelle, Umphress and Gee, 2002). The conceptual development of duty as a motive and the empirical evaluation and testing is still in its infancy and it has yet to await its import to economics and CG theories. The lack of presence in our theories does not excuse its absence in our teaching but put even stronger demands to include it in our teaching, and ultimately, to develop it through our studies. I will therefore continue to describe duty through contrasting it to the other motives.

Duty in contrast with selfishness and belongingness

Economic agents of today are claimed to be motivated by two different forces, the instinct of selfishness and the instinct of belongingness, represented by two different perspectives on humans, the economic man and the social man. I would like to add the moral man that acts out of duty.

Agency theory has as its starting point the claim that every individual is

governed by self-interest. This is, as argued by Granovetter (1985), an under-socialised view of human action and human motives to action, creating the image of man as "...close to being a social moron." (Sen, 1977: 336). On the other hand, sociological studies tend to stress internalization and group behaviour, i.e., belongingness or affinity to such an extent that they reach a view of action and motives that is over-socialised.

I extend the classes of human actions from two to three classes. A human being, I claim, is governed by the instinct of self-interest, the instinct of belongingness, and the instinct of duty. They are termed instincts because they are not subject to individual choice, but belong to the faculties of humans. Each instinct have been explored; the instinct of self-interest in economics, the instinct of belongingness in sociology and psychology, but the instinct of duty only in parts and bits in sociology and practical philosophy, and to a lesser degree in economics through the growing interest in business ethics (e.g. Victor & Cullen, 1988).

The exploration of duty is still in commence in economics and business administration. The omission of one significant human motivation to action can maybe be explained by the image of Uomo d'onore that has been created by the endless stream of entertainment movies of the Sicilian and Italian mafia, or the image of the Prussian Junker, that led by duty went to war. It can, however, be found in political studies, such as public policy formation (Kriesi and Jegen, 2000), based on the Weber notion of the different types of action: instrumentally rational, value rational, affectual and traditional. In this categorization, studies in business administration have been focused on instrumental rationality, as in agency theory, or traditional action, as in institutional theory, where imitation and isomorphism are important concepts. The value rational (wertrational) action, which can be expressed as duty, has overall been neglected.

One study approaching duty were offered as early as 1975, explaining professional organizations as implementers of value-rational action (Satow, 1975). It did not, however, get any followers and went into oblivion. A model of normative behaviour has been presented by Etzioni (1988). It has continued into the research areas of business ethics (Victor & Cullen, 1988) and corporate social performance (Swanson, 1995), leaving the case

of duty unexplored. In the field of corporate governance, it has been expressed in a descriptive way by the stewardship view (Davis, Schoorman & Donaldson, 1997), stressing the duty of fiduciary responsibility. White (2004) presented a Kantian conception of duty, pushing duty into the model of preferences and utilities, but at the price of not being able to offer an answer to the question, why being moral (Campbell and Christopher, 1996), i.e., giving up the necessary assumption of the autonomous human that have the freedom of making the choice of acting out of duty. Beugré (2010) argued conceptually that deontic agents, i.e., individuals acting out of duty, could resist socialization into norms of corruption in organizations.

There are several reasons why an agent of duty can be conceivable in economic environments. One reason is using the Perrow (1986) notion of human flexibility, asking the question; under what conditions will an individual behave according to the instinct of self-interest, belongingness and duty? Experiments have showed that individuals tend to act more in accordance to fairness than self-interest when the other players are identified as persons (Camerer and Thaler, 1995), i.e., the instinct of belongingness can be triggered by identity of the exchange partner. Thus, situation and environment stimulate certain behaviour. Empirical studies of ethical climates (Victor & Cullen, 1988; Cullen, Parboteeah & Victor, 2003) appear to support this argument. Another reason is that it is conceivable that certain environments, for example those experiencing high uncertainty, select individuals that act according to duty (White, 2004). Thus, behaviour guided by duty could be selected by the environment.

My claim is that there are, at least, three models of the human being in the economic sphere, based on three instincts, with capacity to predict human behaviour. I add duty, and therefore I will now show that there is a conceptual space available for duty.

Self-interest is when an individual act upon a calculus where the costs and benefits for the individual are summed together through a preference function into a utility which produce the action. There are no limitations of the behaviour, thus even opportunistic acts and illegal acts are included since it is only the calculus that put the limits on the behaviour. Self-interest is the rationality behind an action that economics has made hegemonic, deeming all actions to be explained through the calculus of individual utility.

Incentive systems are those organizational instruments that are used to manipulate the instinct and create desirable actions. This is the behaviour of the agent appearing in agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

The need of belongingness is the attitude treated by sociologists (Baumeister and Leary, 1995; Cremer and Leonardelli, 2003; Gere and MacDonald, 2010), claiming that humans have a tendency to belong to groups, and to adjust to the norms of the group (Blair & Stout, 2001). In order to be accepted in the group, an individual internalize norms, i.e., becomes socialized, or act in a way that is considered to be legitimate, for example reciprocity and inequity aversion (Fehr and Fischbacher, 2002). This instinct can have rather simple modern manifestations, such as supporters of a football team, or in more advanced and totalitarian systems, with the function of creating a coherent society, such as religion (Graham and Haidt, 2010). The sanction system of the group is governing this instinct, where the ultimate sanction is the exclusion from the group.

The need to do the right thing signifies the tendency of humans to experience a duty (Blair & Stout, 2001), which is an action that is being performed because the individual considers the action to be obligatory. It is a normative behaviour in the sense that it rests on an order that the individual carry, but it is not defined by a group, but by the individual. Thus, it has to be clearly separated from the instinct of belongingness, where the group through their ideology defines the proper behaviour. Duty is not something that is performed, as in the instinct of belongingness, in order to please the group and to be accepted by the group. An action governed by duty is performed because it is right and because it has to be performed.

The motivation to perform actions according to the different instincts differs. The self-interest motivation is with reference to the individual, the motivation of belongingness has a reference to the group, and the duty has a reference to the righteous order and its rules. As claimed by Kantian moral philosophy, which I will present in the next section, a duty is not performed out of inclination, be it towards the self or others. It is without desire, except the desire to perform the duty.

The instinct of belongingness and the instinct of duty are both behaviours governed by internalized norms. A major difference between these two instincts is that the sense of belongingness is tied to a group and the feelings

for the group, while the sense of duty, according to Kant, is tied to practical Reason. We transpose it into *Weltanschauung*, which is a system of ideas that define the proper actions the actor has to perform, i.e., to paraphrase the honourable men of the Wild West: ‘an actor has to do, what an actor has to do’.

Duty is an instinct that governs human rational action through relating action alternatives to a *Weltanschauung* that indicate what actions have to be performed, without reference to individual or social utility, but to what is righteous. It cannot be reduced to corporate social responsibility (CSR) or other similar approaches since they are teleological models, thus not being in accordance to duty, which is a deontological model.

It should be stressed that although being claimed to be instincts, they vary between individuals, depending on the individual history. It has been found, for example, that Kibbutz children, trained in a highly cooperative culture, are more prone to cooperate than children from middle-class city environments in Israel (Shapira, 1976; Shapira and Madsen, 1969), and that children from Israeli Kibbutz and Germany are more cooperative and less competitive in behaviour than Israeli and American city children (Madsen and Shapira, 1977). It has also been found that moral judgement differs between cultures, as defined by ethnicity, nationality and class (Haidt, Koller and Dias, 1993). Thus, it can be claimed that environment, such as culture, do not remove any instinct, but influence its application.

In order to develop the view of duty, I now turn to a description of duty, using my interpretation of the Kantian moral idea.

Kantian duty

The human being is heteronomous in the sense that she is influenced by her desire to happiness, to life and to be accepted in a group. These are the driving forces of selfishness and belongingness. The individual being makes decisions and acts out of a calculus how to improve her individual utility or social acceptance. She thereby becomes a function of her calculus and the situation for her as biological being or social being. She is dependent of something outside her i.e., she is heteronomous.

The human being is, however, also autonomous, and it is her autonomy that is the subject of the Kantian moral teaching (Kant, 2004). She has the possibility to act out of freedom, independent of any outside force that

stimulate her to perform an action. Freedom can, however, not be proved, but only indicated as a necessary assumption in order to explain the existence of the moral order. In this sense Freedom is for the practical Reason what *Das Ding an Sich* is for the pure Reason, a necessary assumption, but which we can have no knowledge about, and therefore never can prove. It is, however, a necessary assumption in order to understand morality. The human being has the possibility to formulate categorical imperatives, which are rules for the will, thus she is free since only those that are free can formulate rules for themselves. Freedom is the capacity to regulate your self, independent of situation and circumstances.

The human regulation of her will is the moral law, which is contained in the practical Reason, as compared to the pure Reason, where the principles of knowledge reside. As an individual she creates maxims, i.e., rules of her conduct, for example, 'I will take care of anyone that needs me'. Confronted with a human that needs care, she has the free choice of taking care of the person, or to walk by. The assaulted person in the Gospel according to St. Luke (10:29-37) could be left behind, as the priest did since the person were not a Jew, or could be taking care of, as the Samaritan did, since the suffering person was a human being. The morally correct action is not to adhere to maxims, but to confront your maxims with the categorical imperative, the ultimate regulation of the free will. It says, in two famous formulations that: 1. "Act only according to that maxim whereby you can at the same time will that it should become a universal law." ("Handle nur nach derjenigen Maxime, durch die du zugleich wollen kannst, dass sie ein allgemeines Gesetz werde"), and 2. "Act in such a way that you treat humanity, whether in your own person or in the person of any other, never merely as a means to an end, but always at the same time as an end" ("Handle so, dass du die Menschheit sowohl in deiner Person, als in der Person eines jeden anderen jederzeit zugleich als Zweck, niemals bloß als Mittel brauchst."). Since the assaulted person is a human being, she has to be treated as an end, i.e., taking care of, thus, according to the first formulation, the maxim of taking care of others is morally correct since it can be a universal law.

The correct moral actions are those actions that are in accordance to maxims that can be made universal laws. The Kantian moral system is

therefore a deontological moral system, where the morality comes from acting according to certain maxims. This can be compared to moral systems, like the utilitarian, that is a teleological moral system since it judges a moral action out of its consequences. The morally correct action is not when you apply a calculus and find out that the action can produce something considered as good. If you do that, you are not free, but ruled by the consequences of your actions. Instead, you have to adhere to the maxim and act in accordance to it. If the rule stands the test of the categorical imperative, you have made a morally correct action.

Duty (Pflicht in German) is the action performed out of reverence of the maxim that is in accordance to the categorical imperative. It is not obeying the maxim, it is not to act because it is in accordance to a duty where the duty tells you how to act, since then the duty is the cause of the action, and thereby it is not a free act. Duty in the moral sense is not to perform due to duty, but out of duty. It is paying respect to a maxim, to act, not in accordance to a duty, but because it is a duty. Therefore, duty can be pleasant or unpleasant, but both of these are personal feelings and sentiments arrived at during the act, which are consequences, and therefore without any moral value. Duty is performed since it is right, which is the only reason, the only cause of the act. Through duty the human being manifest herself as a being with practical reason, vanquish her biology and her social needs, realizing her freedom and manifest her as an intelligible being.

This sense of being noble, when only listening to her own Reason, is termed self worth or self-respect. It should, of course, not be interpreted as an argument of subjectivity and individualism, since Reason is a faculty of all intelligible beings. It is truly universal, not being tied to any individual sentiments and occasional feelings, or to any democratic feelings, trying to satisfy a group or a majority of humans, since moral standards are not subject for voting but for the categorical imperative. Duty is universal, although self-respect is individual.

We transpose this idea of one single universal Reason into a system of ideas held in esteem by an individual, which we term Weltanschauung. It could be translated into World view, but we are not sure that the English term connotes the very content of Weltanschauung, being a set-up of

ideas and beliefs that make it possible for the individual to understand the world and to interact with the world, i.e., the concept is both a concept of cognition and of action. While world view is probably only a system of ideas, which excludes it from being a concept of moral, Weltanschauung includes praxis, thus stressing action, and thereby being a concept of morality. We also realize that transposing practical Reason to Weltanschauung is controversial, but space is here limited and arguments would divert attention from my exploration of duty. I am confined with the comment that universal Reason runs the risk of being reduced to the liberal contractual conception of the original position, as presented by Rawls (1989), which present society as devoid one of its very basic elements, that of conflict. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Categorical_imperative - cite_note-Ellington-0#cite_note-Ellington-0

Summarizing, it can be said that duty is to perform an act that follows a maxim that has been evaluated by the individual using the categorical imperative with reference to a Weltanschauung. Duty manifests the individual as a free, autonomous and intelligible being (i.e., carrier of practical Reason) with self-respect.

Conclusion

Humans have at least three different motives for their actions, selfishness, belongingness and duty. While teaching and research in business programs deals with the two first, the third alternative, duty, is mainly ignored. I have showed in this paper that there is a conceptual space for the third motive, duty. Through duty we can understand human action when it is driven by motives of doing the right thing instead of satisfying the needs of the ego or the group. Methodological it can be hard to identify duty since the dominance of selfishness and belongingness makes humans inclined to motivate their actions through the hegemonic and therefore legitimate motives of selfishness or belongingness. But science has the responsibility to find the explanation to action, not only to find the legitimation of action.

Academics, through their research, but even more, through their teaching, influence individuals, their actions and ultimately, society. Society expects that we realize what we communicate. We have therefore to realize what we communicate. To understand the width of human behaviour and action

is the task of social science, including business administration and economics. Therefore, we include duty as a human motive of action, together with selfishness and belongingness.

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